

STUDY ON WOMEN'S KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE IN PRE & POST MATERNAL HEALTH CARE IN SOUTH 24 PRAGANAS DISTRICT OF WEST BENGAL, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Maternal health care is defined as comprehensive care to improve all round health of the mothers during Ante natal Period, Intra natal period and Post natal period. The study was conducted in purposively selected Diamond Harbour-1 block from where; eight Gram Panchayets and 17 Sub Centre's selected from South 24 Parganas district in West Bengal. Total 121 no. of respondents were selected as Study population in sub-center, comprised of all the reproductive age group of 18-45 years women. The collected data was analyzed by using SPSS based statistical tools for conclusion. The study revealed that, maximum no's of respondents had knowledge and practice on anti-natal, Intra-natal and post natal care as- TT injection, Nutritious feeding, Urine test for pregnancy, health checkup, breast feeding, provide nutritious food and family planning method, which is very much indicative for making accessible maternal and child health services in the state of West Bengal, India.

Key Words: Knowledge, Practice, Women, Maternal, Health care, pre-natal, Post natal etc.

INTRODUCTION

The health of mothers and children reflects the well-being of a society. The right to health is a fundamental part of our human rights and of our understanding of a life in dignity. The right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health, to give its full name, is not new. 'Primary health care' is the first level of contact of individuals, the family and community with the national system, where "Primary Health Care" is provided. The purpose of Primary Health Care Services is to improve the health status of the population.

It was advocated that the provision of Primary Health Care should be within a framework of an integrated health services. Maternal and Child health care is important component of

primary health care services. Maternal health care is defined as comprehensive care to improve all round health of the mothers during Ante natal Period, Intra natal period and Post natal period. Practices are defined as the observable actions of pregnant women that could affect her health and reflect her behavioral changes on utilization of maternal health care services. Available knowledge and practice are effective in reducing maternal and newborn suffering and death. Health promotion programs worldwide have long been premised on the idea that providing knowledge about causes of ill health and choices available will go a long way towards promoting a change in an individual's behavior towards more beneficial health seeking behavior. In this context, the study was concerned about knowledge and practice in Pre & Post Maternal Health Care in South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal, India.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The study was conducted in purposively selected Diamond Harbour-1 block of South 24 Parganas district in West Bengal. There are eight Gram Panchayets and 17 Sub Centre's (SCs) in the selected block of the district. One Sub Centre was chosen within one Gram Panchayets. So 08 Sub-centers, out of 17 Sub-centers were selected for study. For research study, Sub Centre was selected as a sampling unit as Sub-Centre is the peripheral outpost of existing health delivery system in rural area and provides all the primary health care services related to Maternal and Child Health. Data was collected from those respondents who were registered in Sub-Centers in the month of January 2013 for accessing maternity services and availing services throughout the factors associated with it during pregnancy, care of delivery and post-partum period. Total 121 no. of respondents were selected as Study population in sub-center, comprised of all the reproductive age group of 18-45 years women. The knowledge of respondents in different stages (ANC, INC and PNC) was dependent variables along with 14 no's of various independent variables were analyzed in the study. Quantitative and qualitative data collection method was carried out during January, 2013 to December 2013. The collected data were tabulated and analysis was done by using SPSS version (16.0) through Percentages Analysis, Chi- square test and binary logistic regression for conclusion from the investigative study.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The research study was concerned to find out the difference of women's knowledge and practice according to four groups on items of Antenatal care (ANC), Intra natal (INC) and Post natal care (PNC). Therefore, the study was conducted to identify four categories of knowledge and practice as '**No Knowledge No Practice (K⁻P⁻)**', '**Practice without Knowledge (K⁻P⁺)**', '**Knowledge without Practice (K⁺P⁻)**', '**Practice with Knowledge (K⁺P⁺)**'.

The Table-01 represents the percentage of different groups related to women's knowledge and practice during Antenatal period. In item-1 representing 'Urine test for pregnancy' it is seen that majority (90 %) of study population were in group (K⁺P⁺) who both had knowledge and practice and (5.0%) women were in (K⁻P⁺) and (K⁺P⁻) groups each. There was no respondent in (K⁻P⁻) group. Item 2 'representing 'Urine test to SC' the most (35.6%) of women were in (K⁺P⁺) group, followed by (33.9%) women in (K⁺P⁻) group and (16.5%) women in (K⁻P⁻). The least number (14%) of respondents were in (K⁻P⁺) group. Again it is

seen that, maximum women (41.4%) and (41.3%) were in two groups (K^+P^+) and (K^+P^-) whereas (9.9%) women in (K^-P^-) group, who had no knowledge about registration must be done within 3-4 months of pregnancy and did not register their name within 3-4 months of pregnancy and (7.4 %) women in (K^+P^-) group who had knowledge but did not 'Registered within 3-4 months' (item 3). It is found that the women who checked their health four times, maximum (42.1%) respondents were in (K^+P^+) group and minimum (13.2%) respondents in (K^+P^-) group, whereas (K^+P^+) group had checked their health four times (24.9%) and (K^-P^-) group had no checked their health four times (19.8%) women respectively (item 4). The majority (63.6%) of the study population belonged to (K^+P^+) group and minimum (2.5%) in (K^-P^-) group. Again among (K^+P^+) group, (29.8%) respondents took 'Dose of TT injections timely' which was more (4.1%) than women in (K^+P^-) group. In case of item 6 'IFA tablets provided from SC', maximum (38%) women were in (K^+P^+) group and minimum (19%) women in (K^+P^-) group. Whereas (22.3%) and (20.7%) women were in (K^-P^-) and (K^+P^+) groups respectively. Next, On item 7 'Extra amount of food', maximum (66.1%) women were among (K^+P^+) group, who knew the importance of extra amount of food and took extra food during pregnancy and minimum (5.8%) women in (K^-P^-) groups, who did not know and did not practice on it. Rest of (19%) women were in (K^+P^-) group, who knew about extra amount of food intake but did not practiced, and (9.1%) women were in (K^-P^-) did not know but took extra food during pregnancy. Item 8 '2 hrs rest in day time' among (K^+P^+) group, (69.4%) women were more than other groups (K^+P^-) and (K^-P^-) by women (28.1%) and (2.5%) respectively. There was no one in group (K^-P^-). Other item 9 '8 hrs rest in night time', majority women (36.4%) of study population were in (K^+P^+) group and followed by (28.9%) women in (K^+P^-), (24.0%) women in (K^-P^-) and (10.7%) women in (K^+P^-) groups respectively. Item 10, 'Nutritious food provided from AWC' maximum (51.2%) of women were in this group (K^+P^+) whereas (4.1%) women in (K^+P^-) group. Among (K^+P^+) group (38%) women were more than (6.7%) women in (K^-P^-) group. It was seen that maximum (38%) women were in group (K^+P^+) who had knowledge in the medicine took by prescribed doctors and took medicine where (14.9%) women were in (K^-P^-) group who did not know and did not practice. Again among (K^+P^+) group who knew and did not take medicine, which was prescribed by doctors (36.4 %) women were more than (10.7%) women in (K^+P^-) group, who did not know but took medicine was prescribed by doctor.

The findings analyzed that, respondents were maximum in (K^+P^+) group, who had knowledge and practiced in case of seven items as 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8 & 11 during Ante-Natal period. For this, it was point out that most of the women were aware and had knowledge on ante-natal services, also they had practiced it. Again maximum no of respondents were in (K^+P^-) group, who had knowledge and did not practice on item 6. As reasoned that women knew and were aware about the importance of IFA tablets. So, they were collected 100 IFA tablets from SC, but they did not consume it properly. Respondents stated that, they did not like it as they felt vomiting or physical disturbance after consumed tablets, so negligence might be one of vital reason for non-consuming tablets. Next, women were maximum among (K^-P^-) group who had no knowledge but practiced on four items as 4, 9 & 10. Due to lack of awareness, they did not know about the importance of items but they did practice it.

Respondents informed that health professional i.e. ASHA worker went to their house regularly and motivated them to take ante natal care and advised them to take personal care during pregnancy. *Acharya and Cleland's (2000)* study had appreciated the contribution of village health workers for making maternal and child health services accessible particularly for women. *et al. (2005); Chandhiok et al. (2006); Simkhada et al. (2008); Muhamad (2011) & Raksha and Shameem (2016)* found significant relationship of women's knowledge and practice during anti-natal period for availing various primary health care practices.

Table-01: Frequency distribution of different groups related to knowledge and practice during Ante Natal stage

Sl. No	Items	K ⁻ P ⁻		K ⁻ P ⁺		K ⁺ P ⁻		K ⁺ P ⁺		Total
		Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	
1	Urine test for pregnancy	0	0	6	5.0	6	5.0	109	90.0	121
2	Urine test to SC	20	16.5	17	14.0	41	33.9	43	35.6	121
3	Registration within 3-4 months	12	9.9	50	41.3	9	7.4	50	41.4	121
4	Four times health check up	24	19.8	51	42.1	16	13.2	30	24.9	121
5	Dose of TT injections timely	3	2.5	36	29.8	5	4.1	77	63.6	121
6	IFA tablets provided From SC	27	22.3	23	19.0	46	38.0	25	20.7	121
7	Extra amount of food	7	5.8	11	9.1	23	19.0	80	66.1	121
8	2 hours rest in day time	0	0	3	2.5	34	28.1	84	69.4	121
9	8 hours rest in night time	29	24.0	44	36.4	13	10.7	35	28.9	121
10	Nutritious food provided from AWC	8	6.7	62	51.2	5	4.1	46	38.0	121
11	Medicine prescribed by doctor	18	14.9	13	10.7	44	36.4	46	38.0	121

From Table -02, found out percentage analysis of different groups related to knowledge and practice during Intra Natal period.

It was seen that, in the study population, among (K⁻P⁻) group, the (57%) of respondents were maximum and minimum (9.1%) of women were in this (K⁺P⁺) group on item-1 'Matrizan facility', whereas (22.3%) women in (K⁺P⁻) group, (11.6%) women in (K⁻P⁺) group. During Intra natal period, maximum (66.1%) women were presented in (K⁺P⁻) group who knew about importance of 'Institutional delivery' (item 2) but they did not go to hospital for birth and minimum (7.4%) of women were presented in (K⁻P⁺) group who did not know but they went to hospital for delivery. Whereas (17.4%) women and (9.1%) women were

presented in (K⁻P⁻) group and (K⁺P⁺) group respectively. In study population, it was showed that item 3 'Home delivery by trained personnel', maximum (88.2%) of women were involved in (K⁺P⁺) group and followed by (11.8%) women in (K⁺P⁻) group. There were no respondents in (K⁻P⁻) and (K⁺P⁻) groups.

It was seen that, among (K⁺P⁺) group, (79.4%) women were maximum than (20.6%) women among (K⁻P⁺) group on item 4 'Five cleans for home delivery' and there were no respondents in (K⁻P⁻) and (K⁺P⁻) groups. Next majority (50.0%) of respondents were involved among (K⁺P⁻) group, on item 5 'Rs.500/- given from SC.' and followed by (38.3%) women in (K⁺P⁺), (8.8%) women in (K⁻P⁺) and (2.9%) women in (K⁻P⁻) groups respectively. Above the result it was concluded that two items as 3 and 4, maximum women were presented in group (K⁺P⁺) who had knowledge and did practice during Intra natal care. Again in case of two items as 2 and 5, majority of women were presented in (K⁻P⁻) group, who had knowledge but did not practice. As reasoned for item 2 'Institutional delivery' respondents commented that they had knowledge on importance of institutional delivery but they did not go to hospital for delivery because they might be felt shy and embarrassed to be assisted by male doctors during delivery time and they also felt fear due to bad behaviour of nurse in hospital another importance reason might be long distance of hospital from respondent's house. As reasoned for item 5 that respondents knew about facilities of JananiSurakhaYojana scheme and they did not access its facilities from Sub center due to unavailability of mother's identity proof documents or unopened individual bank account. Rests of item 1, maximum women were presented among (K⁻P⁻) groups. *Salam and Siddiqui (2006); Pandey et al. (2007); Garg et al. (2010) & Mutreja and Kumar (2015)* conducted study to assess the knowledge and practices of women on maternal and child health during Intra-natal period and found that most respondents (70.9%) gave correct answer that at the age of six months a child can be given other food in addition to breastmilk.

Table-02: Frequency distribution of different groups related to Knowledge and practice during Intra natal period

Sl. No	Items	K ⁻ P ⁻		K ⁻ P ⁺		K ⁺ P ⁻		K ⁺ P ⁺		Total
		Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	
1	MatriZan facility	69	57.0	14	11.6	27	22.3	11	9.1	121
2	Institutional delivery	21	17.4	9	7.4	80	66.1	11	9.1	121
3	Home delivery by Trained personnel	0	0	4	11.8	0	0	30	88.2	34
4	Five cleans for home delivery	0	0	7	20.6	0	0	27	79.4	34
5	Rs 500/- given from SC	1	2.9	3	8.8	17	50.0	13	38.3	34

Table-03 shows that percentage analysis of different group related knowledge and practice

during Post natal period. On item 1 '3 times health checkup' women (45.5%) of study population were maximum among (K⁺P⁺) group where minimum (4.1%) women were in (K⁻P⁻) groups. Again (35.5%) women were in (K⁻P⁺) group who had no knowledge on 3 time health check up must be done but they went to SC for 3 times health checkup whereas (14.9%) women were in (K⁺P⁻) group who had knowledge on importance of '3 times health checkup' but they did not go to health checkup 3 times to during Post natal care (item1). Next the most (43%) of mothers were presented in (K⁻P⁻) group whereas (30.6%) and (19%) women were involved in (K⁻P⁺) and (K⁺P⁺) groups. Less percentage (7.4%) of women was in (K⁺P⁻) group on 'Time of colostrum feeding' (item 2). It was seen that on item 3 'Times of Exclusive breast feeding' maximum (47.9%) of respondents were in (K⁺P⁺) group and followed by (24.8%) respondents in (K⁻P⁻), (19.8%) respondents in (K⁺P⁻) group and (7.5%) respondents in (K⁻P⁺) groups. In case of item 4 'Nutritious food provided from AWC', (43.8%) respondents were maximum among (K⁺P⁺) group whereas (23.1%) women were (K⁻P⁻) group, (17.4%) women in (K⁻P⁺) group and (15.7%) women in (K⁺P⁻) group respectively. It was seen that maximum (72.7%) women were in (K⁺P⁺) group who had knowledge on importance 'use of family planning' and they also used family planning methods, whereas least (9.1%) women were in (K⁻P⁻) group who did not know about family planning methods and did not use methods. Again (18.2%) women were in (K⁺P⁻) who had knowledge but did not use family planning methods where no one was found in (K⁻P⁺) group who was unknown and unused of family planning methods (item 5). The majority (52.9%) of women were in (K⁻P⁻) group who did not know about the family planning methods (oral pills, condom) are provided from Sub Centre and they never collect the methods from SC for using it whereas (5.8%) women belonged to (K⁻P⁺) group who did not know that method are provided from SC but they collected methods from health worker & used it. Among (K⁺P⁺) group who had knowledge on methods are provided from SC, (28.1%) women were maximum than 13.2% women were in (K⁺P⁻) who had knowledge on 'Method provided from SC' but they did not collect methods from SC (item 6).

Above result analyzed that maximum percentage of respondents were involved among (K⁺P⁺) group who had knowledge and practiced on four items such as item 1, 3,4 & 5. Rests of two items as 2 & 6, maximum respondents were involved among (K⁻P⁻) group. For this reasoned respondents informed that there was lack of information and less interest among them on importance of colostrum's feeding timely and contraceptive methods provided from Sub centre. Here, study was interested in whether there is relationship in between Religion (independent variables) and Age at marriage, Religion and Age at first pregnancy, Religion and Parity, Religion and Family type, Religion and Family size. *Mustafa (2005); Kishore et al. (2009); Deepti (2010) & Singh et al. (2012)* conducted a study to assess knowledge and practice regarding post natal care and found that that early breast feeding knowledge and practice were suboptimal among the mothers in rural study area.

Table-03: Frequency distribution of different groups related to knowledge and practice during Post Natal period

Sl. No	Items	K ⁻ P ⁻		K ⁻ P ⁺		K ⁺ P ⁻		K ⁺ P ⁺		Total
		Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	Fr	%	
1	3 times health check up	5	4.1	43	35.5	18	14.9	55	45.5	121
2	Time of Colostrum feeding	52	43.0	37	30.6	9	7.4	23	19.0	121
3	Time of Exclusive breast feeding	30	24.8	9	7.5	24	19.8	58	47.9	121
4	Nutritious food provided from AWC	28	23.1	21	17.4	19	15.7	53	43.8	121
5	Use of Family Planning methods	11	9.1	0	0	22	18.2	88	72.7	121
6	Methods provided from SC	64	52.9	7	5.8	16	13.2	34	28.1	121

CONCLUSION

The study revealed the status of knowledge and practice during ante-natal, intra-natal and post natal period as pre and posts maternal health care of the women respondents in the study area. The findings analyzed that, respondents were maximum in (K⁺P⁺) group, who had knowledge and practiced in various practices during Ante-Natal period. Maximum no of respondents were in (K⁺P⁻) group, who had knowledge and aware about the importance of IFA tablets but did not consume, as they felt vomiting or physical disturbance after consumed tablets, so negligence might be one of vital reason for non-consuming tablets. The study found that, the health professional i.e. ASHA worker went to their house regularly and motivated them to take ante natal care and advised them to take personal care during pregnancy. Considering Intra-natal care, the majority of respondents had knowledge on importance of institutional delivery but they did not go to hospital for delivery, because they might be felt shy and embarrassed to be assisted by male doctors during delivery time and they also felt fear due to bad behaviour of nurse in hospital another importance reason might be long distance of hospital from respondent's house. The respondents also knew about facilities of JananiSurakhaYojana scheme, but they did not access its facilities from Sub center due to unavailability of mother's identity proof documents or unopened individual bank account. The study finally revealed that, maximum no's of respondents had knowledge and practice on post natal care as-health checkup, breast feeding, provide nutritious food and family planning method, which is very much indicative for making accessible maternal and child health services in the state of West Bengal, India.

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